

THE ROLE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION AND THE IMPORTANCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS IN TEACHING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights the importance of information technology in educational processes and the essential role of modern technology in both teaching and learning.

Information technology is an integral part of every domain of education. In many ways, technology is profoundly changing the way teachers teach and students learn. Books were rare in medieval times and only an elite few had access to educational opportunities. At those times, individuals had to travel to centres of learning places to get educational resources, however, today massive amounts of information including books, audios, images and videos are available to utilize at one's fingertips through the Internet. Technology is a powerful tool that can support and transform education in many possible ways, from making it easier for teachers to create learning materials to enabling new methods and techniques for students to learn and work together.

The quora that is held in debate.org website indicates that about 60 % of people assume that teachers' role in education is irreplaceable. Surely, teachers can use

technology to have a greater impact but it is never termed as a replacement for a trained and caring teacher, though.

Nowadays, it seems even impossible to imagine global education system without modern technologies, during pandemic this prospective strongly proved itself. The internet has allowed for a number of technological tools to come into the classroom as well. Initially, giving plus sides of technology is acceptable.

1. **Special needs of students.** There are plenty of applications that satisfy students' requirements and they give a great pleasure of learning. Distance learning and computer technology activities massively do a favour to bridge the gap between regular and disabled students.

2. **Access to numerous resources immediately.** Before long, students were used to bringing heavy copybooks to class, but now most of copybooks are available online. Additionally, e-books, online

activities and educational games are easy to be accessed so that the learning process is streamlined and effective. Many educational institutions offer online courses, video conference and applications such as Skype and Zoom are platform that provides comfortable knowledge sharing.

3. **New approach.** The assessment process in many places is digitalized which means students can do test online and submit their ready home tasks through platforms. Luckily, online platforms gives the opportunity of assessing knowledge base. Teachers do not have to separate long hours to check tasks or assessment and students do not need to wait their results for ages!

4. An opportunity to learn different ways. Technology also provides an opportunity of trying various things that were impossible in the past. Video games can lead to alteration of students' behavior. They offer a n abundant of information and make them become problem solvers. Next, e-versions of every book are amazing, if a student has a trouble with finding resources from libraries to do any home tasks, he can click the button to find any materials from the Net. Online libraries save money, time and everything!

5. Prevention of the boring environment. Learning tools that are in visual or audio format, presentations and animations appeal to learners with fascinating teaching styles. Those who find classroom education boring are effectively persuaded to study through the digital aids that propose an excellence of learning and fun.

6. Cheating. Some online applications do not make cheating secret and reveals plagiarism in a second. Such a golden opportunity gives a hand to teachers in

order to get to know whether the assignment is plagiarized or not.

A lot of students among the world were absolutely discouraged due to the long-lasting risk of Covid -19. Many thought that after some months staying alive would be the key element of the 21st century, so there was not an immediate demand for studying. However, bright thinkers from every part of the globe did their best to deal with the problematic issue as soon as they could. Unbelievable educational applications came out in short period of time. Pre-recorded lessons also served to allow students from different time zones to learn at their convenience. With video calling services such as Zoom, online lessons became the most common measure adopted by educational institutions. Though there were plenty of resources on the internet, the pandemic had shed a light on some brilliant and free options that were not well-known before. Apart from free ed-tech tools, the resources also included open digital libraries. These offered students and teachers all over the free world access to a new array of learning materials. Students who were after self-teaching or learning a new skill were taking advantage of such platforms to continue studying during lockdowns.

The COVID-19 has resulted in schools shut all across the globe, due to this, over 1.2 million children were out of the classroom as education system has changed dramatically with the noticeable rise of e-learning. As it is clear that the COVID-19, a highly contagious infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome, brought only bad days whereas it developed the ways teachers teach students. Surprisingly, there have already been

remarkable transitions amongst many universities. Let's take an example of Zhejiang University managed to get more than 5000 courses online just two weeks into the transition with the help of 'Ding Talk ZJU'. Like other countries, in Uzbekistan the government had announced closure of all educational institutions. During the pandemic, it was felt that education can play a critical role in protecting public health, keeping children safe, ensuring continuity of teaching and learning. Therefore, it was essential for governments all over the world to deal with the issues by formulating adaptive, coherent, and flexible education responses

to the current crisis. UNICEF Uzbekistan was one of the first international organization that got its act together and supported the Government of Uzbekistan's response in education sphere. It was obvious from the planning stage that the most appropriate method of providing distance learning in Uzbekistan is through television, broadcasting video lessons. In addition, the video lessons were also made available for students to access any time through the "Online maktab" telegram channel with around 84000 subscribers. While what the pandemic year did the Earth was severe, it also changed many things for the better.

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